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SESSION 1 A SUSTAINABILITY AND DURABILITY (1)

Geosynthetics, a key brick of the energy transition

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Abstract. To establish a fully green energy system in Europe, flexible energy management is vital, especially with intermittent sources like wind and solar. As part of the TREASURE project financed by the European Union the pit thermal energy storage (PTES) technology is developed further, and it is aimed to streamline the implementation of this type of storage facility which is critical to the realization of a zero-carbon energy system. PTES are essential for utilizing renewable energy in heating communities and industries, hence geosynthetic products play a key role. The potential in Europe has a cumulative estimated capacity in the range of 35 to 110 TWh. This corresponds to a total water volume between 1 to 3 billion m³, at a forward/return temperature of 60/90 °C as used in most European district heating networks. Assuming a water volume from 250,000 to 500,000 m³ per individual PTES, a potential from 2,000 to 12,000 PTES needs to be constructed, although in many cases the water volume can be smaller, with a simultaneous increase in the number of facilities. To waterproof bottom, sides and floating cover of just one PTES with 250,000 m³ Volume ca. 50,000 m² of sealing system is required, for 500,000 m³ it is ca. 78,000 m², which means a European market potential from 160 to 600 million m² for geomembranes exposed to high temperatures.

1 Introduction

The EU Green Deal prioritizes a fully decarbonized European energy system by 2050. To ensure this, energy sectors need to be highly flexible in supply and demand, for the successful uptake of intermittent renewable sources. Flexibility also allows for easier coupling of energy sectors (heating, cooling, electricity) and for increasing the overall energy system efficiency. In the heating sector, energy demand can fluctuate drastically over the course of the year depending on the climate conditions, with the peak demand occurring during the coldest months in winter. On the contrary, the availability of renewable heat sources such as solar thermal heat is highest during the warm sunny months of summer, while most waste heat streams are available all year round. To bridge the temporal mismatch in supply and demand and therefore maximising the share of renewables and waste heat in the heating sector, large-scale seasonal thermal energy storages must play a central role in district heating networks.

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The present knowledge about large thermal energy storage is restricted to a small number of projects, mainly in Denmark and based largely on seasonal storage of excess solar heat.

The EU-funded TREASURE project is aimed at ensuring robust, safe, cost effective and sustainable large-scale thermal energy storage, developing secure and smart system integration concepts and increasing the effectiveness of realizing the pit thermal energy storage (PTES) technology in Europe. In the project seven Pit Thermal Energy Storage (PTES) demonstrators in five different countries are developed. It also has a constant interchange with a group of 16 satellite initiatives, collecting its experiences and feeding them with knowledge and experiences from TREASURE.

Geosynthetic materials, especially geomembranes, play a particularly important role in the PTES technology, as large quantities of hot water have to be stored in a watertight reservoir in order to accumulate thermal energy. Such a reservoir typically takes the form of a large inverted truncated pyramid, see figure 1 below.

Fig. 1. Basic design of a PTES [1]

The particular advantage of this shape, apart from the benefits of relative ease of construction, lies in its scalability to enormous sizes. This allows very large quantities of water to be stored as a prerequisite for correspondingly large quantities of thermal energy under atmospheric pressure. At the same time, however, the requirements for the polymers used pose a challenge. Especially those materials in direct contact with hot water temperatures at 90 °C or more must be able to achieve a long service life. In addition, the potential size and shape of a PTES can lead to difficulties in finding suitable locations. The attempt of this paper is therefore to provide an outlook on the potential for geosynthetics, particularly for waterproofing systems.

2 Current Situation

Traditionally, district heating systems relied on fossil fuels, that could easily match supply with demand. However, with the EU's ambitious goal to phase out fossil fuels by 2050, a swift integration of renewable and waste heat sources is needed. These sources, while abundant, often pose a challenge due to their intermittent availability and mismatch with peak demand periods.

To bridge this gap, Thermal Energy Storage (TES) emerges as a pivotal solution. TES allows us to store excess heat during periods of abundance and release it when demand peaks. One promising TES system to focus on is Pit Thermal Energy Storage (PTES), which offers flexibility and efficiency in heat storage. Denmark has led the way in PTES technology, demonstrating its effectiveness in various applications. However, expanding PTES systems across Europe requires addressing technical, economic, and environmental considerations unique to different regions.

3 Role of Geosynthetics in PTES

3.1 Waterproofing

In principle, a PTES consists mainly of five components: Earthworks, waterproofing system, the energy storage medium water, an insulating floating cover construction and an inlet/outlet arrangement to pump the water around for energy exchange.

The role of geosynthetics for PTES systems therefore lies primarily in sealing the earthworks to accommodate the storage medium. And the importance of a simple, large-area seal is emphasized by the contour and the associated scalability of the structure. According to [2] a design in different shapes is possible, but “an excavation as a truncated pyramid placed upside down in the ground” is the most straightforward form. This form supports the approach of a mass balance of the necessary earthworks, which improves economic efficiency by minimizing soil transport and handling. The soil from the excavation is then used to construct the surrounding embankments with a typical inclination of 1:2, but in general depending on the geotechnical properties of the excavated material. This contour is then made watertight, which also includes the water surface. An insulating cover construction is applied to a floating geomembrane to prevent heat loss from the heated water. Figure 2 shows the principle of the simple construction method with an inclination of 1:2 to reach mass balance.

Fig. 2. Principle of a cross section [2]

The main requirement for the waterproofing system is that the geomembrane used must be able to achieve a service life of at least 20 to 25 years in an environment with typically high temperatures. Depending on the system integration of a PTES, a possible exposure condition can be a high water temperature only intermittently or a permanent water temperature of up to 95 °C. High water temperatures have consequences for the approach to material selection. For example, 25,000 m² of a new type of Polypropylene liner were used in the 70,000 m³ PTES in Høje Taastrup, Denmark, commissioned in early 2023, to fulfil the requirements of at least 20 years of service life at 90 °C continuous temperature load [3]. This specific PTES is the first of its kind as it is operated as a weekly buffer storage and thus demands permanent high temperatures in the uppermost water layer. The methods for accelerated ageing testing of plastics described in [4; 5] have been considered in the material selection process.

Compared to e.g. aquifer TES or borehole TES, PTES technology has advantages in scaling both the total amount of energy per unit (the water volume at atmospheric pressure) and the loading and unloading capacity, since in comparison to the other Large Thermal Energy Storage (LTES) technologies mentioned above, no rock interacts with the heat transfer medium water.

3.2 Reduction of the area

One challenge and difficulty with PTES systems is that such facility consumes a relatively large amount of space, especially compared to other LTES variants, which predominantly utilise deeper layers of the subsurface. The outer dimensions of the dam construction can in many respects lead to difficulties in site selection if this is offset by land costs and other particular interests such as urban utilisation scenarios. Increasing the angle of inclination of the inside and outside of the dams offers advantages for the land consumption of a PTES, which would open up a wide range of applications for geosynthetics in the course of reinforced earth solutions. It also improves the surface/volume ratio in terms of the efficiency of the system, which according to the Danish Energy Agency [6] is a “key figure for heat loss per amount of energy stored”.

An increase in the slope gradient (α) also means that the excavation depth (d_{exc}) can be significantly reduced if mass balance is applied, and the water column remains unchanged. A less deep excavation pit also offers potential in terms of facilitating the earthworks from a technical and economic point of view (Table 1).

Table 1. Influence of the slope inclination on the area consumption.

α [°]	250,000 m ³			500,000 m ³			A_{red} [%]
	a [m]	A [m ²]	d_{exc} [m]	a [m]	A [m ²]	d_{exc} [m]	
26.6°	167	27,959	16.6	205	42,111	21.5	-
33.7°	157	24,536	15.5	192	36,849	19	12
45.0°	146	21,191	13.9	178	31,709	17	25
53.1°	140	19,558	12.8	171	29,207	15	30

As the need for steeper slopes can be highly dependent on the local conditions of each individual plant, a more detailed quantification of potentials is not provided in this paper. In addition, no commercial PTES has yet been equipped with reinforced embankments. However, this approach is being investigated further as part of the German research project “Efficient Pit” [7].

4 Market Potential for PTES

The total District Heating (DH) final energy consumption in 2018 in the EU was 446 TWh, 12% of final energy consumption for space heating and water, with a total installed capacity of 354 GW, with biggest EU markets being Germany (124 TWh consumed, 95 GW installed capacity), Poland (65 TWh/55 GW), Sweden (51 TWh/43 GW), Finland (34 TWh/24 GW), Denmark (31 TWh/25 GW), France (26 TWh/23 GW). [8] It is estimated that in 2021 there were approximately 10,000 heating networks [9] in Europe, representing 12% of EU’s heat demand and serving approximately 60 million EU citizens. The current socio-economic and geo-political context (Russia-Ukraine, FitFor55 package) indicates that the District Heating and Cooling (DHC) market will grow exponentially in the EU. This statement is confirmed by the 2050 roadmaps of EU countries, where radical increase is expected in the next three decades confirming the potential of District Heating and Cooling to further integrate renewable heat sources, harvest the potential of renewable electrification but also to offer an effective energy storage solution [10]. The latest IEA report indicates that in 2021 DH

production increased by around 3% compared to 2020. 25% more heat was delivered to end-users through DH in 2021 than in 2020 [11]. If the strong urbanisation trend continues and appropriate investments are put in place, district heating could meet almost half of Europe’s heat demand by 2050 [12], meaning an increase with a factor 4 (Table 2).

Table 2. DH market share projections for some of the biggest DH markets [10].

Country	Presently	2030	2040 – 2050
Germany	14%	16%	21 – 25%
Denmark	65%	70%	70%
Sweden	50%	Slight increase	
Finland	38%	45% – 50%	
France	6%	10%	15% – 20%
Czech Republic	38%	40%	43% – 47%

As we can see, most major European markets are planning to extend their District Heating and Cooling market towards 2050, increasing the market potential for other important solutions with which the DH systems are to be coupled, such as PTES. Other studies also indicate a rapid growth in the thermal storage capacity, for instance, for the Nordic and Baltic market the project Flex4RES investigated how sector coupling between different energy systems can support the integration of high shares of wind- and solar power in the Nordic-Baltic energy system [13]. Four scenarios are calculated. The preconditions are that 50% of the district heating market is covered by electricity. In all scenarios, it is economically feasible to implement long term thermal storage. The optimal storage capacity is between 1,169 GWh and 1,360 GWh in the four scenarios in 2050.

In the Heat Roadmap Europe 4 (HRE4) project, the possibilities for extension of district heating have been investigated for the 14 EU member states with the largest heat demands. Halmstad University’s database for cities with district heating and cooling systems has been used for the analysis [14]. The project covers 3,207 out of 4,843 district energy systems in the database. One of the findings in the project is that 2,188 district heating systems have either power plants, waste-to-energy plants, or excess heat from industries in the DH area, or in fewer than 20 km, and 64% of the excess heat activities in the countries were found within that 20 km from the DH systems. Altogether there are many existing large DH systems with CHP, and since the utilization of excess heat is only starting to kick off, this amount will be increased significantly in the coming years

5 Derivation of an outlook for waterproofing solutions

With the above information, it is possible to derive the assumed total capacity attributable to PTES as part of annual heat sales in the EU by 2050. This capacity depends on the configuration of the hot water system, the mix of heat sources used; it can vary drastically due to operating temperatures and the size limitations in different networks. Therefore, and to give an order of magnitude of the required operation, 5%, 10% and 15% are considered as the total storage capacity of the annual heat sales to outline scenarios for the geosynthetics industry. For this purpose, as aforementioned the EU-wide annual heat sales in district heating in 2018, the growth factor for the year 2050 and an assumption of a share of PTES as part of large-scale heat storage in district heating networks are considered together as follows.

$$Q_{EU-wide\ 2018} (TWh) = 446 \tag{1}$$

$$Growth\ Factor\ 2050 = 4 \tag{2}$$

$$PTES\ share\ assumption\ 2050 = 40\% \tag{3}$$

The percentage share of PTES capacity of annual heat sales for the three scenarios is then the product of aforementioned PTES share assumption and the scenario consideration:

$$\text{share 5\% scenario} = 0.04 \times 0.05 = 2\% \quad (4)$$

$$\text{share 10\% scenario} = 0.04 \times 0.10 = 4\% \quad (5)$$

$$\text{share 15\% scenario} = 0.04 \times 0.15 = 6\% \quad (6)$$

The assumed total capacity attributable to PTES as part of the annual heat sales in the EU up to 2050 with these 3 scenarios is then calculated as follows.

$$Q_{PTES} \text{ (GWh)} = \text{Scenario} \times Q_{EU\text{-wide } 2018} \times \text{Growth Factor } 2050$$

The corresponding total water volume can be derived by firstly converting the formula for the heat quantity to the corresponding total mass.:

$$m_{total} \text{ (kg)} = Q_{PTES} / (c_{water} \Delta T) \quad (7)$$

The applied temperature difference results from the difference between the forward and return temperatures. In most European district heating networks 60/90 °C is commonly used.

$$\Delta T \text{ (K)} = T_{forward} - T_{return} = 90 \text{ °C} - 60 \text{ °C} = 30 \quad (8)$$

The specific heat capacity of Water is as follows:

$$c \text{ (Kj / kg K)} = 4.20 \quad (9)$$

$$c \text{ (kWh / kg K)} = 0.0011667 \quad (10)$$

Due to the scale, the total mass value is converted into gigatons.

$$m_{total} \text{ (Gt)} = m \text{ (kg)} / 1\,000\,000\,000 \quad (11)$$

An average density of water (H₂O) of 1,000 kg/m³ is then used to calculate the total water volume for the scenarios in 2050 resulting from the total mass. The assumption in equation 12 is simplified since a change in water temperatures, even though undoubtedly occurring in a PTES, does not have a significant impact on the considerations in this document to derive the outlook for waterproofing solutions.

$$\rho \text{ (kg / m}^3\text{)} = 1\,000 \quad (12)$$

$$V_{total} \text{ (m}^3\text{)} = m_{total} / \rho \quad (13)$$

The total volume is then distributed in two different sizes of PTES mentioned under 3.2, 250,000 m³ and 500,000 m³, to represent an approximate number of this kind of large thermal energy storage that would be needed to fulfil the three scenarios in 2050. The results are shown below in **table 3**. To enable a better classification of the orders of magnitude, the two example variables are listed individually with the corresponding values.

Table 3. Quantity of PTES with 250,000 or 500,000 m³ of water; assumed forecast up to 2050.

PTES capacity of annual heat sales		Q [GWh]	m [Gt]	V [10 ⁶ m ³]	250,000 m ³	500,000 m ³
5%	2%	35,680	1,019	1,019	4,078	2,039
10%	4%	71,360	2,039	2,039	8,155	4,078
15%	6%	107,040	3,058	3,058	12,233	6,117

Example for 1 Unit of 250,000 m ³	8.75	0.25	0.25	1	0.5
Example for 1 Unit of 500,000 m ³	17.50	0.50	0.50	0.5	1

The area to be sealed per PTES unit always refers to the basin floor, the embankments and the water surface and from this context a total area (1 layer) can be derived from the number of facilities to be built. With an assumed material thickness *d* of 2 to 3 mm for the geomembranes used and the area assumptions, a potential total material quantity forecast is possible. To waterproof bottom, sides and floating cover of just one PTES with 250.000 m³ Volume ca. 50.000 m² of sealing system is required, for 500.000 m³ it is ca. 78.000 m². Forecasted total volumes are shown in **table 4**.

Table 4. Order of magnitude for geomembrane quantity in dependence of PTES size; assumed forecast up to 2050.

250 000 m ³	A [m ²]	Total Quantity [t]		
		d = 2,0 mm	d = 2,5 mm	d = 3,0 mm
Example for 1 Unit	50 000	100	125	150
4 078	203 885 714	407 771	509 714	611 657
8 155	407 771 429	815 543	1 019 429	1 223 314
12 233	611 657 143	1 223 314	1 529 143	1 834 971
<hr/>				
500 000 m ³				
Example for 1 Unit	78 000	156	195	234
2 039	159 030 857	318 062	397 577	477 093
4 078	318 061 714	636 123	795 154	954 185
6 117	477 092 571	954 185	1 192 731	1 431 278

Thus, depending on the size of the PTES and the thickness of the liner material, a total geomembrane quantity in the range of 0.4 to 1.4 Mton is assumed to be needed.

6 Carbon Footprint Reduction

Quantifying the potential total reduction of carbon emissions as result of PTES implementation is not readily possible, since the potential compilation of different components, assets, requirements and framework conditions in each individual power and heating system varies from one to another.

To, however, give an impression of how a PTES can already contribute to carbon footprint reductions of an energy system and furthermore lead to economical improvements of the same system, the case study PTES Høje Taastrup shall be used as an example instead. This PTES is used for peak load shaving and thus represents a fundamental enhancement of the functional possibilities of this type of large thermal energy storage, away from pure seasonal heat storage. Figure 3 illustrates the setup of the PTES in the district heating network, where it is charged with thermal energy from the transmission network that connects multiple power assets in the capital city and the Greater Copenhagen area with each other. After storing the thermal energy, it is then discharged when needed into the local district distribution network of the Høje Taastrup district.

Fig. 3. Setup of the PTES in Høje Taastrup [15]

According to calculations made by Ea Energianalyse the PTES offers a substantial contribution to the district heating network and power system [16; 17]. Peak shaving the combined heat and power plants leads to an annual CO₂ reduction of 3,000 tons, primarily as a result of saved fossil gas. Another 3,200 tons reduction of CO₂ footprint result from the electricity sector due to optimized electricity production possibilities. In relation to the volume of 70,000 m³ this means an annual greenhouse gas reduction of 43kg of CO₂ per m³ for savings in peak shaving and 43kg of CO₂ per m³ from the electricity sector, which is to some extent transferable to other locations as fossil gas is often used to handle peak loads. In addition to this, the entire system profits from a forecasted 1,05 Mio€ annual benefits due to less expenses on fossil, reduced peaks etc., while the construction costs of the PTES itself are around 76 €/m³ [18].

7 Conclusion

Transformation of energy systems to decrease carbon footprint is an essential approach to reduce the impact on the global climate. Large-scale thermal energy storage is seen as a key to the transformation of the heating sector. In particular, Pit Thermal Energy Storages is a technology with great potential as it offers many opportunities for existing energy systems. The EU-funded TREASURE project aims to establish the technology across Europe, as the use of these systems offers great potential for CO₂ reduction.

Suitable geomembranes represent a core component for the sealing solution, for which, as shown, considerable volumes can be expected. Geosynthetics are therefore of particular importance in this context with the potential to become a key brick of the energy transition.

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